

Women Empowerment – Challenges and Benefits

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Abstract

Women’s empowerments have become a significant topic of discussion in development and economic. It can also point to approached regarding other trivialized genders in a particular social or political context. The Empowering women to participate fully in economic life across all sector is essential to build stronger economics, achieves internationally agreed goals for development and sustainability, and improving the quality of life for women, men, families, and communities. The power or authority to be authorized, especially by legal or official means. A local ordinance empowerment the board of the health to close unsanitary restaurants. Women empowerment should be defined in very simple words that it is make women powerful so that they can take their own decisions regarding their lives and well being in the family and society. It is empowerment women to make them able to get their real rights in the society. Women’s Empowerment Principle to Equality Means Business. Empowering women to participate fully in economically life across all sectors is essential to build stronger economies, achieve international agreed goals for development and sustainability, and improving the quality of life for women, men, families, and communities. As we all know that India is a male dominate country where are males dominate in every area, and females are forced to been responsible for only family care.

Introduction

Empowerment of women and the improvement of their political, social, economic, and health status is a highly important. Also it is essential for the achievement of sustainable development. The participation of both women and men is having required in productive and reproductive life, then including share responsibility for the care and nurture of children and maintenance of the households. The women are facing threats to their lives, health and well as well a result of being overburdened with work of power and influence. In most regions of the world, women receiving less formal educationally than men, and at the same time, women’s knowledge, abilities, and coping mechanisms often gone unrecognized. The power relationship that impede women’s attainment of healthy and fulfill lives operated at many levels of society, from the most personal to the highly public.

Achieving change required policy and programme actions that will improve women’s access to secure livelihoods and economic resources all women, alleviate their extreme responsibilities about housework, remove legal impediments to their participation in

the public life, and raise social awareness through effective programmed of education and mass communication. Also, improve the status of women also enhances their decision and making capacity at all levels in all spheres of life, especially in this sexuality and reproduction. The long-term success of populations programmed. Experience shows that population and development programme has most effective.

A Position of Women in India

Women were denied the right to educational and widow remarriage. They were denied the right to inheritance and ownership of the properties. Many social evils like child marriage and dowry system surface and starting to engulf women. The status of women immensely deteriorates. Dowry became an institutions, and Sati Pratha became prominent.

During the British Raj, many social reformer such as Raja Rammohun Roy, Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar, and Jyotirao Phule starting agitation for the empowerment of women. Its efforts led to the abolition of Sati and the formulation of the Widow Remarriage Act. Stalwarts like Mahatma Gandhi and Pt. Nehru advocate women's rights. As a result of their concentrate efforts, the status of women in social, economic, and political life began to elevate in India.

The Current Scenario of Women Empowerment

The ideas championed by our found fathers for women empowerment, much social, economic, and political provision were incorporated in the Indian. Women now participated in areas such as educational, sports, political, social media, Art, Culture, Service sector and science and technology. But due to the deep-rooted patriarchal mentality in Indian societies, women are still victimized, humiliated, tortured and exploited. Even after almost seven decades of Independence for women are subjects to discrimination in the social, economic, and educational fields.

Rights & Individual Right

Woman is a been with senses, imagination, and thoughts, she can be able to express them freely. An Individual empowerment means to having the self-confidence to articulate and asserted the power to negotiate and decide.

Social Women Empowerment

A critical part of the social empowerment of women is the promotion of gender equality. Gender equality imply a society in where women and men enjoy the same opportunity, rights and obligations in all spheres of the life.

Educationally Women Empowerment

It is empowerment women with the knowledge, skills, and self-confidence necessary to participated fully in the developing process. It means make women aware of their right and developing confidence to claim them.

Economic/Occupationally Empowerment

The implies for better qualities of materials life through sustainable livelihoods own and manage by women. It means reducing their financial depending on their male counterparts by make them a significant parts of the human resource of the life.

Legal-Women Empowerment

The provision of an effective legal structures that is supportive of women empowerment. In the addressing gaps between what the law prescribes and what occurs for women.

Political-Women Empowerment

The existence of a political system favored the participation in control by the women of the political decision making processing in governance.

Women Empowerment Challenges

Perspective

A most widespread and dehumanizing discriminations against women are on the basic on the biased perspective. Discrimination against the girl child begins from birth itself. The female infanticide is a common practice in India. The ordeal that an Indian girl faces at birth is only the beginning of a lifelong struggle to be seen and heard.

Patriarchates Bottleneck

The traditional Indian societies is a patriarchal societies rule by the diktats of self-proclaimed caste lords who are the guardians of archaic and unjust traditions. They put the burden of traditions, cultures, and honor on the women and mark their growth. The incidences of honor killing reveal the distorter social fiber in the male dominated society. Women constitute only 29 percent of the workforce but form the majority of the destitute in the country. There has been a failure in transforming the available women base into human resources.

Loopholes in the Legal Structure

Although there are number of several laws to protect women against all sorts of violence yet, there has been a significant increasing in the episodes of rapes, extortions, acid, and attack. This is due to delay in legal procedure and the presence of several loopholes in the function of a judicially systems.

Lack of Political for women

The still-pending Women's Reservation Bill underscoring the lack of political have to empower women politically. The male dominance prevails in the politics of women are forced to remain muted spectator. Way ahead started with bridging the deep-rooted biases through sustained reconditioning. It is only possible by promoting the ideas of gender equality and uprooting the social ideology of male child preferred to ability. This concept of equalities can be first developing in every household, it should be taken to the society. This can be achieved by run sustains aware programs with the help of Nukkad Natak or dramas, radio, television, etc.

The Necessity of Women Empowerment

Without women's empowerment, we cannot remove injustice and gender bias and inequalities.

1. If women are not empowerment, they can't enjoying security and protect in life.
2. It is provides them a safe working environment.
3. The Empowerment Acts as a powerfully tool against the exploitation and harassment of women.
4. To get adequate legal protection for women.
5. If not socially and economically empowerment, women can't develop their own identities.
6. If women are not employed, the global economic will be adversely affected as women constitute a vast chunk of the world's population.
7. Women are highly creative and intelligent, which makes it imperative to receive their contribution to socio-economic activities.
8. For a progressive society, women need to provide equal opportunities for work.

Benefits for Women Empowerment

Women empowerment adds to the confidence of women in abilities to lead meaningful and purposeful lives. It removing their dependence on others and makes than individual in own right.

1. They can lead their lives with dignity and freedom.
2. It adds to their self-esteem.
3. It gives them a distinct identity for women.
4. They can gain positions of respect in society.
5. As they are financially independent, they can spend on all their needs and desires.
6. They can makes meaningful contributing to the well-being of the society.
7. They act as capable citizens to makes the country achieving enhanced GDP growth rates.
8. They get fair and equitable access to availabilities resource of the country.

Conclusion

Empowering woman social, economical, educational, political, and legal is gone to be a Herculean task. It is not gone to be easy to change the culture of disregard of women who are so deep rooted in society. But it doesn't mean that it is implausible. Only revolutions bring changes in a day by day, but reforms taken their time. This particular will take its time as well. The ideas of women empowerment might sound hard by the yard, but by the inch, it is just a cinch. All we want to concentrated effort focus in the right direction that could rest only with the liberated of women from a form of evil. The women Empowerment helps to make the society and world a better place to live in and march forward on the way to inclusive participation. It means to increase happiness for the family and the organizations where women make a difference.

Women's Health and Legal Rights Issues in India

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Right to medical care is important because it relates to the very existence of human life. Medical care is as essential as the other basic needs of a person like food, water, shelter and clothing. Every nation has evolved its own system of laws to ensure the health rights of its citizens. These laws aim to establish a humane system of health care based on the principles of equity, justice and efficiency.

Right to health and health care is a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. This has also been emphasized by the Supreme Court of India in several of its rulings. Article 21 of the Constitution casts a special obligation on the state to protect citizen's life from medical and other forms of negligence.

The Fourth World Conference on Women stated that women have the right to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health. The enjoyment of this right is vital to their life and well-being and their ability to participate in all areas of public and private life. Health has been defined by WHO as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity (WHO, 1946). Thus, women's health should also involve their emotional, social and physical well-being and is determined by the social, political and economic context of their lives, as well as biology. Prevailing laws ensure the well-being of women and grant them equal status in the society.

When we discuss laws related to women's health, it needs to be emphasized that we have to deal with health in its comprehensive meaning. Thus, not only laws specifically related to women's physical, mental or social health are important, but even the laws that empower women are also relevant. This is because women's empowerment is an undisputed determinant of women's health.

Article 42 of the Constitution of India provides: The State shall make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief". And further: "The State shall regard the raising of the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of health as among its primary duties and in particular. The State shall endeavour to bring about prohibition of the consumption except for medicinal purposes of intoxicating drinks and of drugs which are injurious to health' (Article 47).